

Development of Textiles in Ramayana

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Abstract:

As the Ramayan Era is too old i.e., thousands of years back, some people used to say it mythology but it's not a myth. We can observe so many geographical proofs of Ramayana right from Ayodhya - Panchvati -Ramsetu to Shri-Lanka and when you will read it and study you will find amazing facts related to industrial development also. Here we are limiting ourselves up to the development in textiles only. The points related with textiles are limited in Ramayana but the development related with types of fabrics, value addition is surprising. Here, we will go with original Sanskrit Shlokas (verses) one by one to get the information. Note: We are sticking with Valmiki Ramayana (Geeta Press, Gorakhpur) strictly.

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1. Introduction

Ramayana is poetic biography of 'ShriRam', the king of Aayodhya written by Maharshi Valmiki in Sanskrit language. It is thousands of years old. (About number of years there is dispute, nobody can tell perfectly). In this biography seven big Chapters called as 'kand' are there like-1) Balkand 2) Ayodhyakand 3) Aaranyakand 4) Kiskindhakand 5) Sundarkand 6) Yuddhakand and 7) Uttarkand. In these kands, many small chapters called as 'Sargas' are included and these sargas are having number of Shlokas.

For searching these glimpses of Textiles, we have read every shloka and found some significant facts related with development in textiles. This was a gaint task.

Here, we are putting the study in short through following sequence A) Types of fabrics in Ramayana B) Value addition ideas C) Textile products excluding clothing D) A land having Sericulture.

A) Types of fabrics developed in Ramayana:

While studying, we though found the maximum use of silk in clothing, we also found that cotton fabric was also there. The use of skin of a tree is also there but were used for special purpose of going to forest i.e. for vanavasa, we will see one by one.

i. Silk: As Ramayana is story of Kings, silk clothing was used more and more for example.

'Athatma Paridhanarth Sita Kausheyavasini' Shlok 9, Sarg 37, Ayodhyakand'

Here, 'Vasas' means vastra or clothing. Kausheya means derivated from Kosha i.e. nest of a honey bee i.e. silk.

'Seetayaha Kausheyasya pari.' Shlok 14, Sarg 37, Ayodhyakand'

Like this, use of silk for apparels is found there and it is the tradition of Enshant Bharat. Special for devotional rituals, silk is used for so many years.

ii. Cotton: With silk, cotton fabric was also there in use. We found one shloka showing the matter was like this-

'Veshtante tasya langulam jirnaihi karpasikaihi pataihi II Shlok 6, Sarg 53, Sundarkand'

It means to follow the order of 'Ravan' all the servants of him, started winding Hanumanas tail with older cotton cloth.

iii) **Skin of trees:** These wearing were wellknown as ‘Valkal’ or ‘CheerVastra’. The tribals and Hrishis living in forest were wearing these cloths. We will get its references like this-

‘Athatmaparidhanarth Sita Kousheyvasini / Sampreksh Chirn Santrasta Prushati Vaguramiv II Shlok 9, Sarg 37 Ayodhyakand’

It means, when Sita became afraid as she has been asked to wear those rough cloths made by treeskin (Chirvastra) because she had habit to wear silk. Thus, there are references of these three types of fabrics.

B) Value addition ideas in Ramayana:

It is really very surprising observing the modern ideas of textiles used in a history of Ram thousand years back. We will see it now.

We found two remarkable ideas 1) Apparel with flower decoration 2) Saree with Border

i) Apparel with flower decoration:

When Ravan visited Sita to propose her again, he worn very impressive Dhoti. it is mentioned like this.

‘Mathitamrutafenabhamrajoastramuttamam I

Sapushpamavakarshantm saktamangade II Shlok 24, Sarga 18, Sundarkand’

It means like this – His (Ravan’s) wearing was just like colour of fresh butter with high quality. Flowers were attached to his dhoti. At this moment, the dhoti was entangled with the ornaments in his hand and he was trying to make it free.

Thus, this attachment of marval and flowers is really surprising.

We will see another example. It is like this...

‘Niljimutsankashan Hemsanchaditambaram II Shlok 5, Sarg 40, Yudhakand’

i.e. Ravan was looking like dark cloud. He wore the dhoti with golden decoration. In ancient Bharat, it was well known fashion to use gold and silver yarn with silk for decoration purpose. It was well known as ‘Jarikam’.

ii) Saree with Border

Yes! In those days border of different colours was also used and it was used by ‘Anjana’ i.e. mother of Hanuman. It is mentioned with birth story of Hanuman like this.

‘Tasya Vastram Vishalakshya Pitam Raktadsham Subham I’ Shlok 12 Sarga 66 Kishkindhakand’

Jambhavan says that the lady with bigger eyes worn yellow saree with Red border. After observing these important features of apparels or wearing of human being will try to find other products.

C) Textile products :

In Ramayana we have found two three other products related with textiles. We will see one by one.

i) Bed sheets: In Sundarakand, there is information related with bed used by Ravan and silk bedsheets were used on it.

‘Maharhastarapetairuppannam Mahadhanehi I’ Shlok 2, Sarg 10, Sundarkand’

Means costlier bed sheets were used on that bed.

ii) Royal Umbrella (Shwet Chatr)

The royal umbrella of white colour was used by Kings in Ayodhya and Lanka also. Here, we see it with Vibhishan in Lanaka.

‘Ekstatra Maya drustaha Shwetchatro Vibhishanana I Shlok 32, Sarg 27, Sundarakanad’

I have seen only Vibhishan with white umbrella. With this we found rope also.

iii) Rope: Before going to forest for fourteen years, Ram donated everything he was having. Speaking about that he says:

‘Yo hi datwa dwipshreshtam kakshayan kurute manaha I

Rajjusnehen ki tasya tyajatha kunjarttamam II Shlok 3, Sarg 37, Ayodhyakanda’

It means that Ram says-Just I have donated my best elephant, now how can I keep my affection in the rope which was used to tie him? It gives sense that ropes were used to tie the elephant means how much strength was developed in those ropes.

iv) Black thread to wear on west

In ancient days, there was a tradition to wear black thread (multiply) on waist of males called 'Katdora' or Katisutra. It is also mentioned in Ramayan like this

'Shronisutren mahata mechaken susanvruta / Shlok 26 Sarg 22 Sundarkand'

Here, Ravan was wearing this 'shonisutra' i.e., black thread on his waist.

v) Hand gloves: Yes, the fighters at that time were used to wear handgloves but they are made by cow leather. Even if Ram and Laxman were also used to wear those. It is mentioned with the word 'Musttavasasam'. Mushta means palm of hand and vasasam means cover or clothing. The original shlok is like this.

'Dirghasibadhagodhasha Sannadha Mrushtvasasam / Shlok 19, Sarg 3, Ayodhyakanda'

It is mentioned that the Ram and Laxman were having bigger swords with them and they were wearing handgloves made by cow leather for handling of those swords. Now, we will see one more surprising textile product.

vi) Bandage: Now a days. Bandage industries are there. It is one of the most required textile products in medical field. It was surprising when we found the mention of bandage in poetic sense. It is like this.

'Sandhyrogostitaistamrairanteshwapi cha pandubhini / Snigdhairbrapatchaidabhadhavrannmivambaram II Shlok 5, Sarg 28, Kishkindhakand'

It means at the time of evening when the sun is setting down the red sky having white clouds over it seeming that like a white bandage over the wound. The word 'Vranamivambaram' gives this sense as Vrana means wound and ambar means cloth. Such a way by observing various textile products in Ramayana, we will try to find out the manufacturing hub in it.

D) A land having sericulture:

In Ramayan, Vanar King Sugriv was travelled around the world and he was knowing many more facts related with various parts of the world while given this information he mentions one land like this.

'Bhumicha Koshkaranam, BhumichRajatakaram / Shlok 23, Sarg 40, Kishkindhakand'

It means he was giving information about two lands of silk manufacturer and land of silver manufacturers also. Means, at that time manufacturing of silk through sericulture was routine and there were manufacturing hubs just like Tirpur in Tamilnadu.

2. Conclusion:

After going through the literature of Valmiki Ramayana, we found well developed silk production with other fabrics, also we found with various applications of textiles. It is surprising that many more things, modern fashion like bordering the saree with different colour, a land of sericulture, we got the idea of development of textiles in Ramayana and we came to know about great heritage of textile industry.

3. References:

[1] Ramayan by Maharshi Valmiki, Vol. I & II, published by Geeta Press, Gorakhpur.